

The Ways of Decoding Context in Literary Texts

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Abstract

The context has significant consequences with regard to the formation of discourse. In deictic elements indicating place, the location of an event or object is conveyed to the reader and listener through the use of precise or imprecise expressions. The concept of imprecise place is expressed, whereas in the case of "in the town," the concept of precise place is conveyed. In both languages, the expression of precise place deictics is achieved through the use of distance units, whereas imprecise place deictics are conveyed through adverbs of place. Time deictics, in turn, indicate the temporal occurrence of events within a discourse or text, whether precise or imprecise. In both Azerbaijani and English, precise temporal deictics are primarily indicated by the mention of specific periods of the hour or day. In contrast, imprecise temporal deictics indicate the occurrence of an event at a specific time or at an unspecified point in time. In both English and Azerbaijani, temporal context can be expressed by other parts of speech, such as nouns and adjectives, in addition to adverbs. However, the temporal category is largely created by temporal adverbs. In texts and discourse types, a variety of textual deixis, or transition/transitory words, are employed to convey internal meaning to the reader or listener.

Key words: *texts, context, deictic means, pragmatics*

The two related sentences were connected and created a text by means of at first, and in the second sentence by means of later. The given transition or connecting words helped to establish a sequence relationship. Let us consider a sentence from a given literary text in the Azerbaijani language. Thus, dialects of the great language were formed, and sometime later these dialects became completely independent languages.

The expression "sometime later", which provides a sequence relationship in a sentence, helps to establish a logical-semantic relationship of the sentence. In Azerbaijani text linguistics, such connecting words have hardly been studied under a special term.

Concerning their distinctive attributes, if the interconnection is predominantly examined from a grammatical standpoint, more specifically from the perspectives of syntax and semantics, then in discourse, the pragmatic dimension between sender and recipient is deemed to be of greater consequence. As previously stated, the pragmatic characteristics of discourse are contingent upon reference. It is essential to incorporate the proposition into the pragmatic features of discourse. When analysing the informative features of discourse, it is also crucial to determine which idea is conveyed with greater fundamental importance. In contrast, presupposition facilitates the elucidation of the idea in discourse, encompassing the initially postulated idea. Verbs are of greater significance in the revelation of presupposition. In some cases, this phenomenon occurs not only at the expense of the verb but also at the expense of auxiliary parts of speech. To illustrate, the following sentence has recently captured my attention and aroused my enthusiasm: 'Dear Reader, I want to talk to you specifically about a sentence whose inner light I have been

most excited about lately and, of course, in which I have special faith'. In this instance, the function of specific linguistic elements, such as the term 'inner light' and the act of speaking, is significant in both intensifying the meaning and elucidating the presupposition.

With regard to the opening of the term 'inference', P.Grice's theory is of particular importance. Accordingly, the concept, designated by P.Grice as the "conversational maximum," encompasses the intended and understood meanings inherent to the sentence. He posits that the intended and understood meanings are not necessarily aligned and that additional contextual information, or pragmatics, is required to ascertain the intended meaning. P.Grice incorporated this phenomenon into the existing literature as implicature [8, p.194]. To illustrate, in his article "He is an Englishman, so he is very brave," in the sentence, P. Grice sought to elucidate the situation and convey a specific idea to the reader with the aid of words previously designated as transition words.

A number of researchers, including, U.Eco, T.A.Van Dijk, R. de Beaugrand, and N.Fairclough, have conducted research and advanced ideas about the nature and significance of text and discourse, as well as their pragmatic and cognitive aspects. Despite differing opinions regarding the role and significance of text in discourse studies, both linguists and even some philosophers and psychologists consider text and discourse to be important elements in a semiotic sense. In his 1989 article Basic Terms in Text Linguistics, N. Enquist defines discourse as follows: Discourse is defined as "the unity of text and context with a social component"

In both linguistic and interdisciplinary approaches to discourse, the text is considered to be the most significant factor. A text is defined as a language unit that is organised in a hierarchical structure, wherein information is presented in detail according to the degree of significance. The reader will typically focus on the most salient idea within the text hierarchy. Other salient characteristics of texts include the presence of a principal theme, the consolidation of multiple concepts within a single text, and their logical progression, as well as the manifestation of a causal relationship between sentences Text awareness can be defined as the ability of the reader to distinguish the main information in the structure of the text. The most comprehensive account of this topic was provided by S. Mohan. In his view, the hierarchical presentation of information, which he terms "content-based," serves to enhance the coherence and informational value of the text

According to G.Kazimov, sentences are considered components of the text, and these sentences together create a syntactic whole that conveys a thought or idea. One of the main means of connecting syntactic wholes is considered to be prosodic means. Sentences that create syntactic units are divided into opening, developing, and closing sentences to create a microtheme, and these sentences are connected to each other both by special explicit means (i.e., connectors, determinants, etc.) and without special linguistic means (prosody). According to K. Abdullayev, a text is a structure built based on a certain model. Based on the structure of the text, he considered the subject and closing relationship in the syntactic whole to be the basis for conveying meaning. In this case, it is more convenient to clarify the beginning, development, and closing of a small topic called a microtheme. In the expression of a microtheme, both implicit, i.e., "subtextual"-hidden forms and explicit "formal means" are used. The means of conveying any given idea without the need for interpretation can be considered an explicit form. In the given example, there is no need to explain the idea because the syntactic whole manifests itself in the form of a microtext, presenting the meaning to the reader. In texts or microtexts, the

hidden or implicit meaning of the text is accompanied by presupposition. Let us consider the two given examples. I sold my yellow car - in this sentence, it is an indication that only the yellow car was sold and that there are other cars besides it. So, in this example given in English, the presupposition of the sentence is precisely the sale of the yellow car and not the others. In another example, in the sentence *I have no time to spend with you*, the presupposition is precisely the lack of time to spend with someone.

One of the most intriguing aspects of cognitive linguistics is the question of text and meaning. The knowledge present in the text interacts with the participants of the discourse. In recent times, researchers have highlighted the role of psychological factors, as opposed to linguistic ones, in the process of understanding text. The act of understanding a text is influenced by the language used in that text, and vice versa. In texts, there are a number of means of conceptual and semantic interconnection, which collectively form the basis of the thinking process. The occurrence of meanings in a text is dependent on a number of factors, including lexical means, such as the use of synonyms, homonyms, and repetitions, as well as grammatical means, including articles, pronouns, suffixes, and adverbs.

The concepts of situation and context in discourse and texts are of particular importance, and it can be argued that the former is of greater significance in the context of literary texts. Any context can be explained by different situations. In the proverbs that are examples of literary texts, the promotion of waking up early and avoiding laziness is also conveyed, but these concepts are explained in different situations. In the first example, the proverb presented in metaphorical form is contrasted with the proverb given in its direct meaning in the second sentence. The main characteristics of verbal communication include the individual and social characteristics of the addressee and the addresser.

There are some important parameters in the delivery of both discourse and text that serve both expressiveness and communicativeness. For example, the use of modal verbs, adverbs indicating time and place, and expressions to direct attention to the addressee or vice versa, as well as reference, ensures the formation of the text. F.Veysalli, in his textbook "Introduction to Discourse Analysis", classified reference into two groups - anaphoric and cataphoric, and anaphoric means classified references indicating clarity (*and, or, simply, namely*), contradiction (*but, only, however, despite*), reason (*thus, for this reason, therefore*), time (*first, then, finally, initially*) in subgroups. Interestingly, in English, the transitory words we mentioned earlier coincide with this division. However, in English, this division covers more reference groups. G.E. Wishon, in his textbook "Let's Write English," added subgroups such as purpose, result, concession, comparison, and similarity, and augmentation to this division. It should be noted that with the help of such grammatical means, the author can achieve a clearer conveyance of information to the addressee.

We have already noted that one of the most important aspects of narrative in literary texts or discourse types is the features of coherence (integrability) and consistency. This feature, in terms of temporality, is described by the term co-text. If this term, which has no equivalent in Azerbaijani, is presented as mutually connected paragraphs (sometimes it is also used in the form of co-text), the meaning of the term will convey a certain idea.

In literary discourse, forms of address addressed to the addressee are also important. Some of them are metaphorical (this can be considered a more unethical form). For example, "*One day I was walking down the street. A boy with a beard in a carriage coming towards us, and a blonde*

girl with a hat as big as a minaret, passed me like a breeze. I asked my friend who he was. He replied: This is called Mirza Javad oglu Ahmad, and the one next to him is his mother". Two different forms of address, Mirza Javad oglu and mother, are recorded in the text fragment.

The structure of a discourse may exert an influence on the content it conveys. When analysed in terms of theme-rheme relations, as in actual membership, a specific theme represents a concept that is already known, while the rheme introduces new information about it. It can thus be concluded that the main semantic load falls on the rheme. The ordering of words plays a distinctive role in actual membership. In discussing the role of actual membership in the formation of meaning relationships in texts, it was observed that word order in our language is more flexible than in English. Nevertheless, a certain degree of flexibility is also observed in the use of word order in English literary texts. The objective of this discussion is to address the phenomenon of structural change in texts, and its implications for the context of mental properties.

A comparison of text and discourse revealed that they exhibit a greater degree of similarity. Texts are capable of expressing emotions in both written and oral forms. This can be conveyed both verbally, through the use of language, and non-verbally, without the use of words. The term "non-verbal" encompasses a range of communicative behaviours that are not conveyed through spoken language. These include gestures and facial expressions. In written form, despite the limitations of conveying these means of expression, they are nevertheless transmitted to the reader through specific writing forms (such as bold or italics) or punctuation marks, thereby elucidating a particular situation. The aforementioned features indicate that the text is constituted of symbols and signs, and this is realised within a certain context.